



Supplementary Figure 1. Outline cross-sections of all seven tooth crown models created to represent the scope of aquatic-feeding amniote dental morphologies. (A), 'No Ridges (Conical)' model; (B), 'Average Ridges' model; (C), 'Large Ridges' model; (D), 'Rounded Ridges' model; (E), 'Symmetrical Ridges' model; (F), 'Lingual Ridges' model; (G), 'No Ridges (Recurved)' model. All cross-sections were taken at 50% of the total crown height